

Traffic management & MaaS: a public-private collaboration

Patrick Hofman^{1*}, Ruud van den Dries², Nuno Rodrigues³

1. Traffic Engineer, MAP Traffic Management, The Netherlands (patrick.hofman@maptm.nl)
2. Mobility Innovator, MAP Traffic Management, The Netherlands (ruud.vandendries@maptm.nl)
3. Traffic Architect, MAP Traffic Management, The Netherlands (nuno.rodrigues@maptm.nl)

Abstract

Nowadays, traffic management information provided by public road operators (collective information) and private service providers (individual information) is often conflicting. As both parties can strengthen their own services by combining both private and public information, a collaboration seems to be logical. The challenge for this collaboration is addressed by multiple projects, such as SOCRATES 2.0, C-MOBILE and MyCorridor, with each project looking at it from a different perspective. What these three projects have in common is the provision of a set of services which is based on public-private collaboration, the ambition to achieve more efficient traveling and traffic management through this collaboration, and the entry of a new stakeholder between the public and private parties: an intermediary. These three projects are now starting a pilot phase where different intermediary roles will be further developed either in its technical, functional and business components.

Introduction

Private companies, or service providers (SPs), are developing more and more individual smart mobility services, which have impact on operational traffic management of public authorities (PAs). SPs target individual drivers, while PAs target the collective group of users in the road network. As a result, nowadays, both have different, and very often, conflicting objectives, which often results in conflicting information towards road users. As traffic management measurements of PAs strengthen individual smart mobility services and vice versa, a public-private collaboration to exchange information on measurements and services seems to be logical. The main challenge is how to achieve such collaboration.

This challenge is addressed by multiple projects, with each project looking at it from a different perspective. For example, the CEF-project SOCRATES 2.0 (<https://socrates2.org/>) builds upon the ERTICO platform TM2.0 (<https://tm20.org/>) work and aims to demonstrate the feasibility of 'interactive traffic management', which is based on a close cooperation of road authorities, service providers and car industries. Secondly, the H2020-project C-MOBILE (<http://C-MOBILE-project.eu/>) aims to accelerate the large-scale deployment of C-ITS services and simultaneously elaborate how services can be utilized and operated by different (public and private) actors. Finally, the H2020-project MyCorridor (<http://mycorridor.eu/>) intends to add traffic management to the Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) concept. What all three projects have in common is the provision of a set of services which is based on public-private collaboration, and the ambition to achieve more efficient traveling and traffic management through this collaboration.

Socrates2.0

The European project SOCRATES2.0, co-financed by the EC CEF program, eleven public and private organisations work together to develop novel interactive traffic management services. 3 types of services will be tested by at least 9,000 users in the regions of Amsterdam, Antwerp, Copenhagen and Munich. The services include smart route advice in case of events, actual speed and lane advice and local warnings, route advice on environmental zones and road works. The pilots will take place in 2019 and 2020 within motorways, regional roads, urban-interurban and urban roads. Project aim to create more business opportunities for the private partners, a more cost-effective traffic management for the public authorities and better service for the road users.

SOCRATES2.0 works as much as possible with existing techniques to implement the new interactive traffic management services and focus on new ways to cooperate and share information between all public private stakeholders.

In the first report of Activity 2 (Koller-Matschke (2018)) first options for cooperation models and intermediary roles were defined. In following Activity 3 detailed work was done to elaborate further the different cooperation models and intermediary roles and to determine which combinations are to be applied and tested in the use cases (services) in the respective pilot sites.

C-MobILE

In June 2017, the C-MobILE (Accelerating C-ITS Mobility Innovation and depLOyment in Europe) project (2017-2020) was launched under Horizon2020 (the C-MobILE project has received funding from European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 723311) It aims to stimulate large-scale, secure and interoperable C-ITS deployments across Europe and simultaneously elaborate how smart mobility services can be utilized and operated by different actors (<http://C-MobILE-project.eu/>).

Regarding a collaboration between PAs and SPs, C-MobILE is more focused on a method on how to incorporate or connect private sector smart mobility services in/to day-to-day traffic management, with the purpose to harvest the usability of smart mobility services by developing a strategy for the operation and exploitation of smart mobility services in real-time and within varying geographical areas. The goal is a coordinated operation of multiple smart mobility services for traffic management purposes.

To achieve this goal C-MobILE adapted the Dutch Dynamic Traffic Management (DTM) 'control strategy' (CROW, 2017). This control strategy consists of a step-by-step approach for selecting and activating so-called strategies when trying to solve or mitigate a throughput problem with pre-defined policy objectives, which are used to define the importance and function of roads as well as quantitative thresholds for nodes, links, segments and route parts. At this moment, in the control strategy only traditional traffic management services, like traffic lights and ramp meters, are included. In C-MobILE this strategy will be extended by adding smart mobility services.

MyCorridor

In June 2017, the MyCorridor project (2017-2020) was launched under Horizon2020 (the MyCorridor project has received funding from European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 723384). It aims to create a pan-European cross-border MaaS solution for a all kind of travellers, by connecting Service Providers into a One-Stop-Shop to the end-user.

In this day and age, we see a lot of MaaS concepts popping up in various locations and also in various deployment states and variations. They all strive to provide the best end-user experience providing near endless travel solutions from A to B and demising the need for owning private transport. This enables greener and safer transport and it is foreseen it will also provide seamless travel to a group of users who are currently not served by the current-day mobility offerings.

It is foreseen that this will result in more travel demands being for filled and will also catalyse new travel demand, the so-called latent travel demand. This requires service providers to act on this responsibly to avoid that solving traffic jams will result in gridlock in a different transportation system.

MaaS enables travellers to shift from one transportation system onto another. Travellers don't have to be a client of a specific transportation system in order to use it. Travellers can thus use more, if not all, transportation systems that are in operation. Within the MyCorridor project this is done through a so-called One-Stop-Shop. Just one registration to the One-Stop-Shop is required for the traveller to use all provided services within the One-Stop-Shop. This seamless integration of services enables the traveller to move and choose freely how and where to go.

Project results & Discussion

MaaS and traffic management cannot be seen separately anymore, as MaaS evolves through traffic management and traffic management evolves through MaaS. The main challenge is how a common traffic management and MaaS operation can be achieved. In this respect Transport Systems Catapult (Datson et al. (2016)) has developed a reference architecture for Mobility as a Service (MaaS), in which the relations between stakeholders, technologies and capabilities that are involved, are presented. This approach could also be applied to a common operation of traffic management (see Fig. 1). At the centre of the architecture are the actors that make a common operation of traffic management feasible, tangible and visible in terms of its technical functionality.

Fig. 1 Mobility as a Service reference architecture (Datson et al. (2016)) and Traffic management reference architecture

In the introduction mentioned projects, MaaS and/or traffic management are being considered regarding optimising the public-private collaboration. In Socrates2.0 new traffic management collaboration models have been developed, which will be assessed by defined use cases. In C-MobILE a traffic management method has been developed to achieve a coordinated traffic management operation. And in MyCorridor an app has been developed for travellers to plan their (multimodal) trip considering real time traffic information.

In these three projects there is an ongoing discussion on two topics:

1. What does the end user (traveller) want?
2. How should the organisation of this collaboration look like?

Regarding the first topic, it is difficult to define what a traveller wants as a or one traveller does not exist. Each traveller has its own preferences regarding their travel, route, mode and time choice. However, all three projects focus on another aspect of traveller needs.

1. In Socrates2.0 travellers are driving in a car and want to receive route information, such as real time alternative, faster, routes.
2. In C-MobILE travellers are driving in a car and want to receive road information, such as time

to green at traffic lights and in vehicle signage.

3. In MyCorridor travellers are all kinds of people who want to travel from A to B having information available on all possibilities.

While Socrates2.0 and C-Mobile focus on cars, MyCorridor is more focussing on all kinds of travellers.

The second topic, the organisation of such a collaboration, is addressed differently in the three projects:

1. Socrates2.0 has defined multiple collaboration models and chose one model to implement and assess in the project. Next to the traditional stakeholders, such as road authorities and service providers, in Socrates2.0 a new stakeholder has been identified: an intermediary. An intermediary connects multiple road authorities with multiple service providers. The role of this intermediary is twofold.
 1. To monitor traffic and decide whether or not to activate traffic management services;
 2. To assess the impact of the traffic management services. For example, service providers send feedback to the intermediary about the number of vehicles they have rerouted. The intermediary collects this information of all service providers and provides an overview of the total impact of this measure (follow-up of the advices).

In the Socrates2.0 pilots the collaboration model will be implemented and assessed.

2. C-MobILE has developed a traffic management method to achieve a coordinated traffic management operation. This method is based on the Dutch Dynamic Traffic Management (DTM) ‘control strategy’ (CROW, 2017), in which traffic could be managed from a network management point of view. In C-MobILE this method is being programmed in a tool, which will be implemented in a traffic management center in at least one pilot site to assess this method. With access to this tool the traffic management center is able to activate certain smart mobility measures operated by service providers, such as Priority at traffic lights and Mode, Trip and Time advice.
3. MyCorridor has developed a One-Stop-Shop, a platform which connects (transport) service providers and which provides travellers one platform to plan and book their trip. This platform will be implemented and tested in six pilot sites, covering local, urban, interurban and cross-border travels. Travellers can indicate their travel preferences in this platform, which then defines the best travel solution for the travellers also considering real time traffic information.

Conclusions

The results of the pilots in the three projects are expected next year. However, the projects already have gained insight in traveller expectations, which actually provides input for the scope for a public-private collaboration. To provide a good travel advice to travellers, it is important to have all necessary information available. When you are addressing car drivers only, then you should include all information regarding route choice (based on real time traffic information) and price (e.g. tolling). When you address all kind of travellers, this information cannot be limited to route choices and prices or to timetables of public transport, but should include all travel modes, also such as walking, bicycling, car driving and a combination of travel modes, and a real time travel time and price comparison. Even better is to also consider adding ride sharing as a travel mode, which has not been done until now.

To achieve such a system, all stakeholders will have to collaborate in such way that travellers are able to access all information in one application. Although results on operations of such collaboration models are not yet available, we can conclude that information on transport modes needs to be available, preferably at one central point. The same applies to traffic management information. Only then, application providers will be able to provide this information to travellers.

References

- Koller-Matschke, I., 2018. Proposed cooperation framework bottlenecks. In: Socrates 2.0 Activity 2.. https://socrates2.org/application/files/3515/5488/4491/SOCRATES2.0_report_Act2_Cooperation_Framework.pdf
- CROW, 2017. Handboek verkeersmanagement – Module Regelaanpak Werkwijze en richtlijnen voor de inrichting van een regelaanpak voor verkeersmanagement. Versie 2017. https://www.crow.nl/downloads/pdf/verkeer-en-vervoer/publicatie/290a_handboek-verkeersmanagement_module-regelaanpa.aspx
- Datson, J. et al., 2016. Mobility as a service. Exploring the opportunity for mobility as a service in the UK. Transport Systems Catapult, Milton Keynes.